

Experimental Approach to Generating Subcritical Wait-Time Distributions

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ABSTRACT

Low or zero source reactor startup requires robust stochastic models in order to ensure safe operation and avoid potential accident scenarios. In order to use these models in a stochastic point kinetics code for a commercial setting, stringent validation and verification of them with experimental data is required. Current available data is for fast, HEU systems, inadequate for validating for thermal, LEU systems. Using the Inherently Safe Subcritical Assembly at Lawrence Livermore National Laboratory, we developed an experimental framework as a proof of concept before conducting a larger experimental campaign at a more capable critical assembly for generating experimental data for model validation. We present a method for constructing experimental wait-time distributions for a subcritical system using a pulsed neutron generator for 5%, 50%, and 75% duty factors and apply the Zero Precursor Model as a preliminary analysis to collected decay wait-times. This work was able to successfully construct experimental wait-time distributions that yielded adequate results for many reactor kinetics parameters. Future improvements to neutron generator duty factor selection and shielding of the detector array from source neutrons were identified for continued work with the Inherently Safe Subcritical Assembly. Ultimately, the presented work demonstrated our current experimental techniques viable and worthy of exploring more complex analytical models and using more advanced experimental facilities.

Keywords: ISSA, Pulsed Neutron, Wait-time, COG, Subcritical Experiment

1. INTRODUCTION

Neutron sources are commonly used in nuclear reactor startup to minimize the stochastic nature of fissile systems. However, they are costly and present potential safety risks [1, 2]. Low or zero source start-up, also known as blind start-up, avoids these issues, but is generally avoided due to the potential for power excursions without operator knowledge. If this avenue is to be explored, robust and validated stochastic models are required for safety analysis of start-up [3].

In low source start-up or fast-burst reactor environments, the required time to reach or decay to a certain neutron population threshold is known as the wait-time. As these systems are highly stochastic due to the inherently low initial source neutron population, the corresponding wait-time is as well [3, 4]. Thus, to have an accurate understanding of how the system behaves, a cumulative distribution function (CDF) must be created. Gordon et al. [3] presented various novel and historical analytical models, and the solutions to them, for creating the wait-time CDFs, however, in order to use them in a production level code, extensive validation of the models must occur. While there is some available fast-burst reactor data, it is almost exclusively of HEU and fast systems, undesirable for the validation of LEU and thermal spectrum systems of commercial reactors. Zero-power research reactors present as a powerful tool to generate data to validate the stochastic models, but they are required to follow strict regulatory guidelines and would be a more costly way to do so over a dedicated subcritical assembly [3].

This work conducts the proposed subcritical, pulsed neutron experiments by Gordon et al. at the Inherently Safe Subcritical Assembly (ISSA) at Lawrence Livermore National Laboratory (LLNL) as a proof

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of concept of experimental methods for subcritical wait-time experiments. Explored in this paper is how different neutron generator operating parameters affect wait-time CDFs. Currently, this work only employs the Zero Precursor Model using the Bell approximation inversion technique. This work helps gauge what is necessary for an improved campaign of experiments for at a thermal, LEU facility, like the Sandia Pulsed Reactor Facility–Critical Experiments (SPRF/CX).

2. THEORY

Gordon et al. have presented the Zero Precursor Model, a simplified model for creating wait-time CDFs. As the names suggest, this model ignores the contribution of delayed neutrons, an assumed acceptable approximation for ISSA as the delayed neutron precursor population is very minimal in comparison to prompt and source neutron contributions. We followed the proposed subcritical pulsed-neutron experiments of Gordon et al. and used the developed equations to extract relevant reactor kinetics parameters. The equations presented below are explained in a general manner to apply them to wait-time experiments. Williams and Eaton [5] present a complete derivation and explanation of the equations and should be referenced if a more detailed understanding is required.

2.1. Zero Precursor Model

The Zero Precursor Model is a simplified model that considers a subcritical system with a constant, negative reactivity and is spatially and temporally independent. Eq. (1) defines the the CDF $Q(n, t|s)$ for the cumulative probability of a neutron population to reach n in the system at time, t , with a neutron injected into a system at a previous time, s .

$$F(z, t|s) = \sum_{n=0}^{\infty} z^n Q(n, t|s) = \frac{z}{1-z} G_S(z, t|s) \quad (1)$$

The generating function, G_S , is defined for a constant source (G_{S1}) in Eq. (2) and for a time-dependent pulsed neutron source (G_{S2}) in Eq. (3). For both Eqs. (2) and (3), ρ_0 is the subcritical reactivity, Λ is the mean generation time, z is the generating function variable, which is defined to be $0 \leq z \leq 1$, and $H(t)$ is the Heaviside unit function. Eqs. (4) and (5) define η_0 and λ .

$$G_{S1}(z, t|s) = \left[1 + \lambda(1-z) \left(1 - e^{-\rho_0(t-s)/\Lambda} \right) \right]^{-\eta_0} \quad (2)$$

$$G_{S2}(z, t|s) = \exp \left(- \frac{S_p(1-z)e^{-\rho_0(t-\bar{s})/\Lambda}}{1 + \lambda(1-z)(1 - e^{-\rho_0(t-\bar{s})/\Lambda}} H(t - \bar{s}) \right) \quad (3)$$

The generating function can be combined into via, $G_S(z, t|s) = G_{S1}(z, t|s)G_{S2}(z, t|s)$. In these equations, the pulsed source, S_p , is approximated as a delta function. Importantly, the units of the constant background neutron emission, S_0 , are of neutrons per second, where the units of S_p are neutrons per generator pulse.

$$\eta_0 = \frac{2\bar{\nu}S_0\Lambda}{\chi_2} \quad (4)$$

$$\lambda = \frac{\chi_2}{2\bar{\nu}\rho_0} \quad (5)$$

Here, S_0 is the constant source previously defined, $\bar{\nu}$ are the average number of neutrons per fission, and χ_2 is the multiplicity term [6]. This work uses a $\bar{\nu}$ of 2.45 and χ_2 of 4.6. As currently derived, this

method is only accurate within a few dollars of criticality due to the quadratic approximation made for the multiplicities term (χ_2) [7]. For a system like ISSA, where it is almost -9\$ away from critical, this approximation would not be generally acceptable for most theory analysis purposes. However, since the goal was being to develop an experimental framework for conducting pulsed neutron wait-time experiments, we deemed it acceptable for the use of this assumption. To solve for Q in Eq. (1), the function is inverted by using the Bell approximation.

2.1.1. Bell Approximation

The Bell approximation, proposed by Bell [8], is defined in Eq. (6). Here, the generating variable, z , can be roughly approximated by $e^{-1/n}$. This method only works over certain regions of n , and becomes inaccurate for values of n below ~ 100 .

$$Q_S(n, t|s) \approx G_S(e^{-1/n}, t|s) \quad (6)$$

Eqs. (7) and (8) are the analytical wait-time CDF generating functions for the constant source and pulsed source, respectively.

$$Q_{S1}(n, t) = \left[1 + \lambda(1 - e^{-1/n})(1 - e^{-\rho_0 t/\Lambda}) \right]^{-\eta_0} \quad (7)$$

$$Q_{S2}(n, t) = \exp \left(- \frac{S_P(1 - e^{-1/n})e^{-\rho_0(t-\bar{s})/\Lambda}}{1 + \lambda(1 - e^{-1/n})(1 - e^{-\rho_0(t-\bar{s})/\Lambda})} H(t - \bar{s}) \right) \quad (8)$$

The combined Q_S of the constant and pulse sources is $Q_S(n, t) = Q_{S1}Q_{S2}$.

3. EXPERIMENTAL METHODS

3.1. ISSA Facility

ISSA consists of Materials Test Reactor (MTR) type fuel assemblies of highly enriched uranium (93.16%) arranged in a three by three grid and submerged in water. Thus, ISSA can be configured with up to nine total fuel assemblies, allowing for multiple different levels of subcriticality to be achieved, with the highest consisting of nine assemblies and an approximate mass of 2.0879 ± 0.0428 kg of ^{235}U . Each fuel assembly has a total of nineteen fuel plates with gaps between each that serve as interstitial water channels, creating a highly moderated system. The fuel within each plate is a mixture of U_3O_8 and high-purity aluminum powder sandwiched between two solid aluminum plates with each plate holding an overall mass of 12.210 ± 0.250 g of ^{235}U .

The ISSA fuel assemblies and tank are described in detail in the ICSBEP benchmark [9], however it should be noted that the support fixture has been updated since the initial benchmark experiments. The updated structure is completely made out of cast aluminum alloy A356.0-T6 and is a hanging type system, with four arms that hook to the side of the main tank suspending the main containment structure within the tank (see Fig. 1). The main containment structure consists of a bottom plate where the fuel assemblies rest, two spacing grids that evenly space the fuel assemblies and additional structural supports. Additionally, the experiment uses four Reuter-Stokes P4-1636-210 ^3He neutron detectors (5.16 cm in diameter and 100.48 cm in length, at 0.21 MPa) placed on the periphery of the fuel array, but as close to the fuel as possible.

Figure 1. ISSA fuel assembly detector array in drained water tank

3.2. Wait-time Experiments

The wait-time experiments closely followed the pulsed neutron experiments outlined in Gordon et al. [3] with some modifications. The primary difference being the use of a continuous pulsing mode operation of 30 minutes. The pulsed neutron generator used is a Thermo Scientific P 383 D-T neutron generator. The neutron generator was positioned beneath the ISSA tank, with source neutrons directed upward through a pipe that ends below the fuel. The pipe was air filled, allowing unmoderated neutrons to reach the fuel with only having to travel through 6.5 inches water. The system operated with a pulse period of 2 ms and a duty factor, which is the percentage of a single pulse starting from the beginning that is producing neutrons, of 5%, 50%, or 75%. The generator produced approximately 10^8 n/s with an average neutron energy of 14.1 MeV.

3.3. Experimental Wait-time Distribution Generation

The wait-time distributions were constructed in post-processing using list-mode neutron count data as the input. Since a single pulse has too few detection events to provide adequate statistics, analysis is performed on an ensemble of 50 individual pulses superimposed upon one another. Within the ensemble pulse, the active cycle portion of the pulse is discarded, and only the decay section of the pulse is analyzed.

The decay signal is necessary to analyze as any duty factor above a fraction of a percent saturates the neutron signal with both source and prompt neutrons, thus, no system multiplication is visible within the active duration of the pulse. Additionally, the assumption of the neutron beam being collimated from the large water moderation around the source tube is inaccurate. This yields source neutrons directly streaming to the detectors, adding additional noise to the rise-time portion of the detector signal [10]. This flaw can be corrected with modifications to the ISSA facility via adding an absorbing barrier at a lower position in the tank, and by using a D-D neutron generator.

This causes an important shift of how the wait-time, for the purposes of this work, is defined. We define the wait-time as the time it takes to descend from an elevated neutron rate to a user defined threshold. This is an important distinction for how the literature views this problem. Analyses have been done upon the active neutron generator portion of the pulse, however it yielded results much worse than those of the decay portion. A greater discussion of the potential remedies to this will be in

later sections.

Continuing, an array of count rates is constructed using a sliding 50- μ s window. This is then transformed into neutron population via dividing by the geometric efficiency of the ISSA detector array. It has been calculated via simulation that it has an approximate geometric efficiency of 1.2%. It is assumed that the detectors used have 100% intrinsic efficiency and do not suffer from detector deadtime effects, as the count rates are low enough such that minimal effects are observed. A list of wait-times is then constructed by having a series of nested for loops, the first iterating through each super pulse and the second each neutron population estimate at a time step in each super pulse. The corresponding time stamp of when the neutron population falls below the user defined neutron threshold is stored as a single wait-time. Once all wait-times have been collected, the empirical CDF is constructed. The empirical CDF then is fitted using a three parameter (S_p , Λ , and ρ_0) fit of Eq. (8) to create the analytical CDF. Uncertainty estimates of the various parameters are calculated using bootstrap resampling with 1000 iterations upon the ensemble pulse data. All algebraic manipulations of variables used linear propagation of uncertainty and assumed no covariance between parameters.

4. RESULTS

This section presents the experimental wait-time distributions. The results use duty factors of 5%, 50%, and 75% and neutron population thresholds (n^*) of 2E7, 4E7, 6E7, 8E7, and 1E8.

4.1. Cumulative Distribution Results

Fig. 2 gives the experimental and model wait-time cumulative distributions for various n^* . Here, we can see as the n^* threshold increases, the distributions shift towards the left, signifying shorter wait times for the population to decrease below the larger values of n^* threshold. Additionally, there is an apparent waviness of the CDFs, demonstrating that experiment times must be adequately long to achieve a complete distribution of the possible wait-times. The impact of the duty factor is apparent here as well. If the duty factor is too long, it does not leave ample time for the system to fully decay to its initial state before the next neutron pulse. Similarly, if the pulse frequency is too fast, it does not allow for the decay analysis of individual and ensembles pulses. This demonstrates that a neutron generator of high pulse periods and low pulse widths is desirable for running these types of experiments.

Figure 2. Comparison of the experimental (marker and dashed lines) and Zero Precursor Model (solid lines) wait-time distributions for various n^* (continued on next page).

(c) 75% duty factor.

Figure 2. Comparison of the experimental (marker and dashed lines) and Zero Precursor Model (solid lines) wait-time distributions for various n^* (continued).

4.2. Fitted Zero Precursor Model Results

Fig. 3 plot the different fitted parameters across the different duty factors and n^* thresholds. The trends across the different parameters are in agreement with each other, with outliers occurring at the edge points in certain cases, however, certain values tend to fit away from the expected values from COG11.3 Monte Carlo [11] simulations for them. All simulations used the ENDF/B-VIII.0 cross section library [12].

Figure 3. Comparison of fitted Zero Precursor Model parameters across different duty factors and n^* thresholds.

As expected, the estimates of S_p (Fig. 3a) remain generally consistent across the different n^* thresholds, with the exception being at the highest threshold for the 75% duty factor series. Due to the methods used in creating the ensemble pulses for the experiments, this factor is relative to how the data is manipulated.

The fitted values for Λ (Fig. 3b) are underestimated by the model when compared to the COG Λ value. The 5% duty factor result was the closest to the simulated COG value, however, still roughly underestimates Λ by $45.4 \pm 1.0 \mu s$. Across all duty factors, the Λ is underestimated by $49.3 \pm 0.4 \mu s$. It is not currently understood what is causing the overall underestimation, though hypothesized causes are the detector locations or the analog calculation method of Λ by COG. Additionally, it is thought that

the decreasing trend is due to the fact that the high threshold samples from an ensemble pulse that is more effected from the contribution of source neutrons immediately after the pulse ends and shifting the estimated time downwards.

Fig. 4b shows the k_{eff} estimates using the fitted ρ_0 (Fig. 4a) for the various configurations. The ρ_0 produced is prompt reactivity, and is corrected using the COG estimated β_{eff} of 754 ± 7 pcm. After correction, we can see the estimates of k_{eff} are in agreement with each other, with an average difference of -277 ± 180 pcm across all duty factors. The 5% duty produced the lowest difference of -6 ± 317 pcm. Additionally, a lower threshold generally yields better agreement with the COG k_{eff} value.

For the uncertainty, the common trends appear: the uncertainty increases as the threshold values trend away from the middle threshold, and the uncertainty increases as duty factory increases. The first statement occurs due to the rarity of wait-times occurring at the high values and low values of an applied threshold before a new generator pulse occurs. The second is due to the fact that the higher duty factor severely limits the pulse decay time, thus ending a pulse before it is able to decay to a correct threshold level.

Figure 4. Comparison of fitted Zero Precursor Model parameters across different duty factors and n^* thresholds.

5. CONCLUSIONS

This works presents a method to experimentally construct wait-time distributions from pulsed neutron experiments in subcritical systems and compares them to the Zero Precursor Model from Gordon et. al. This preliminary work demonstrates the experimental approach used to construct wait-time distributions, and has a general agreement with presented analytical model. This initial study demonstrates the derived approach warrants a new experimental campaign at a higher capability facility, and the additional exploration into models with delayed neutron precursor concentrations and constant source contributions.

This work has also exposed additional experimental techniques that can be refined for future experiments. Primarily, a neutron generator with an adequately short pulse width to mimic a Dirac delta burst of neutrons, a pulse period long enough for the neutron population to reach the equilibrium population before the subsequent pulse, additional absorbing material between the generator location and detector array, and the use of a DD neutron generator. With these modifications, additional measurements can be conducted at the ISSA facility to see if rise time measurements recording a literature wait-time yield better results than that of the decay analysis. Additionally, an exploratory study into the potential effects of the potential stochastic nature of an individual neutron generator pulse is required to understand the effects it has on measuring a wait-time.

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